

Interpolation Kernel Machine and Indefinite Kernel Methods for Graph Classification

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Abstract. Graph kernels have been studied for a long time and applied among others for graph classification. In this paper we bring two novel aspects into the graph processing community. Currently, the backbone for kernel-based classification is solely the support vector machine. We introduce the interpolation kernel machine for this purpose. In addition, for both support vector machine and interpolation kernel machine, many kernels used in practice do not satisfy the formal requirements (e.g. positive definiteness). We thus introduce extensions of the standard version to indefinite kernel methods. We argue and experimentally demonstrate why these two aspects should be considered for graph classification. One of our conclusions will be that the interpolation kernel machine is a good alternative of support vector machine. Consequently, we will propose an extended experimental protocol. With this work we contribute to increasing the methodological plurality in the graph processing community.

1 Introduction

Kernel-based methods in machine learning have sound mathematical foundation and provide powerful tools in numerous fields. In addition to classification and regression [7,22], they also have successfully contributed to other tasks such as clustering [34], dimensionality reduction (e.g. PCA [15]), consensus learning [25], computer vision [17], and recently to studying deep neural networks [10].

Graph kernels provide a way to compute similarities between graphs [13,16,27]. As such they can be used for graph classification, in particular with Support Vector Machine (SVM) but not only. Graph kernels have been studied for a long time. In this work we address two aspects that are unexplored in the literature so far: interpolation kernel machine (IKM) and indefinite kernel methods.

First, we will look at a particular class of kernel-based classification methods, the so-called IKM, which has undeservedly hardly received attention in the literature. The recent work [3] brought it more attention in the research community and serves as the base of our work. Despite the diversity in the design of graph kernels, their use for classification is rather monotonous, namely by using support vector machines (SVM). This is also reflected in the recent survey papers

for graph kernels: “The criteria used for prediction are SVM for classification” [13]; “We performed classification experiments using the C-SVM implementation LIBSVM” [16]; “In the case of graph kernels, to perform graph classification, we employed a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier and in particular, the LIBSVM implementation” [27]. This is not a surprise due to the dominance of SVM in machine learning in general. However, SVM is not the only choice one can have. In this work we will demonstrate the power of IKM for graph classification.

Second, kernel methods typically require some properties of the kernel function to be satisfied. For instance, the SVM is formulated for positive semidefinite kernels. Similarly, IKMs require positive definite kernels. In practice, however, many kernels are not of these two types. Therefore, the standard version of the kernel method (SVM or IKM) cannot be applied. Instead, we need to apply indefinite kernel methods to cope with such cases.

This paper does not present new methods for graph classification. Instead, it can be understood as a position paper. We bring the two aspects sketched above into the graph processing community. We argue and experimentally demonstrate why they should be considered. One of our conclusions will be that IKM is a good alternative of SVM. Consequently, we will propose an extended experimental protocol that is beyond the currently dominating practice.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. We present the fundamentals of graph kernels in Section 2. The IKM is introduced in Section 3. Then, we discuss the indefinite kernel methods for both SVM and IKM in Section 4. The experimental results are presented in Section 5, which motivates an extended experimental protocol in Section 6. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2 Graph kernels

A kernel function $k(x, y)$ over the space of graphs \mathcal{G} is defined by $k: \mathcal{G} \times \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with a related transformation $\phi: \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_k$ into a Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_k so that $k(x, y) = \langle \phi(x), \phi(y) \rangle$, i.e. the kernel function corresponds to the scalar product in \mathcal{H}_k . If for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and all sets of n graphs, $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n \in \mathcal{G}$, a kernel $k(x, y)$ gives rise to a positive semidefinite kernel (Gram) matrix $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with elements $K(i, j) = k(g_i, g_j)$, then it is called a *positive semidefinite* (PSD) kernel. Making the requirement stronger to ask for positive definite kernel matrix, then the kernel is *positive definite* (PD). Note that the terminology in the literature is not consistent. Some researchers define positive definite kernels as those with positive semidefinite kernel matrix [6]. The terminology used in our work is due to its clarity and helps to avoid potential confusion.

Dozens of graph kernels have been developed [13,16,27], which focus on specific structural properties of graphs. The key design ideas behind these graph kernels differ, e.g. based on Weisfeiler-Lehman test of graph isomorphism [31], paths [4], and graph decomposition [21]. Meanwhile, public graph kernel libraries are also available [12,32].

3 Interpolation kernel machines

Kernels are an efficient way to compute the similarity of two samples in a high dimensional space. In this section we introduce a technique to fully interpolate the training data using kernel functions, known as kernel machines [3,11]. Note that this term has been often used in research papers (e.g. [9,37]), where variants of support vector machines are effectively meant. For the sake of clarity we will use the term “interpolation kernel machine” throughout the paper.

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\} \subset \Omega^n$ be a set of n training samples with their corresponding targets $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\} \subset \mathcal{T}^n$ in the target space. The sets are sorted so that the corresponding training sample and target have the same index. A function $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ interpolates this data iif:

$$f(x_i) = y_i, \quad \forall i \in 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

Representer Theorem Let $k : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a PSD kernel for some domain Ω , X and Y a set of training samples and targets as defined above, and $g : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a strictly monotonically increasing function for regulation. We define E as an error function that calculates the loss L of f on the whole sample set with:

$$E(X, Y) = E((x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n L(f(x_i), y_i) + g(\|f\|) \quad (2)$$

Then, the function $f^* = \operatorname{argmin}_f \{E(X, Y)\}$ that minimizes the error E has the form:

$$f^*(z) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i k(z, x_i) \quad \text{with } \alpha_i \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3)$$

The proof can be found in many textbooks, e.g. [30]. While this statement of the representer theorem gives sufficient conditions on the regularizer, an interesting theoretical extension was given in [1]. The authors showed that an interpolation problem (2) admits solutions representable in the form (3) *if and only if* the regularizer is a nondecreasing function of the Hilbert space norm, thus providing a complete characterization of regularizers that give rise to representer theorems. The recent work [29] studies the same problem in a more general context where the regularizer does not have to be norm-based.

The family of representer theorems like the above is among the fundamental results of learning theory. They allow us to express the optimal solution of certain risk minimization problems in the form (2) as linear combination of expansions in terms of the training samples. Since the various variants of SVM optimization problems can be casted into (2) [30], the representer theorem builds the theoretical foundation for the powerful SVMs. They operate in the finite dimensional space of the training samples mapped into feature space. This is particularly attractive since for many popular PSD kernels, the Hilbert space is known to be infinite dimensional [30].

We now can use f^* from Eq. (3) to interpolate our training data. Note that the only learnable parameters are $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$, a real-valued vector with the same length as the number of training samples. Learning α is equivalent to solving the system of linear equations:

$$K(\alpha_1^*, \dots, \alpha_n^*)^T = (y_1, \dots, y_n)^T \quad (4)$$

where $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the kernel matrix. In case of PD kernel k the kernel matrix K is invertible. Therefore, we can find the optimal α^* to construct f^* by:

$$(\alpha_1^*, \dots, \alpha_n^*)^T = K^{-1}(y_1, \dots, y_n)^T \quad (5)$$

After learning, the interpolation kernel machine then uses the interpolating function from Eq. (3) to make prediction for test samples. Note that solving the optimal parameters α^* in (5) in a naive manner requires computation of order $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ and is thus not feasible for large-scale applications. A highly efficient solver EigenPro has been developed [20] to enable significant speedup for training on GPUs. Another recent work [35] applies an explainable AI technique for sample condensation of interpolation kernel machines.

In this work we focus on classification problems. In this case $f(z)$ is encoded as a one-hot vector $f(z) = (f_1(z), \dots, f_c(z))$ with $c \in \mathbb{N}$ being the number of output classes. This requires c times repeating the learning process above, one for each component of the one-hot vector. This computation can be formulated as follows. Let $A_l = (\alpha_{l1}^*, \dots, \alpha_{ln}^*)$ be the parameters to be learned and $Y_l = (y_{l1}, \dots, y_{ln})$ target values for each component $l = 1, \dots, c$. The learning of interpolation kernel machine becomes:

$$K \underbrace{(A_1^T, \dots, A_c^T)}_A = \underbrace{(Y_1^T, \dots, Y_c^T)}_Y \quad (6)$$

with the unique solution:

$$A = K^{-1} \cdot Y \quad (7)$$

which is the extended version of Eq. (5) for c classes and results in zero error on training data. When predicting a test sample z , the output vector $f(z)$ is not a probability vector in general. The class which gets the highest output value is considered as the predicted class. If needed, e.g. for the purpose of classifier combination, the output vector (z) can also be converted into a probability vector by applying the softmax function. We will explore this option in Section 4.2.

4 Indefinite kernel methods

We first discuss the need of indefinite kernel methods. Then, the different possibilities of indefinite kernel methods will be presented. Due to our focus on IKM in this paper we will start with indefinite IKMs and continue with indefinite SVMs.

4.1 Need of indefinite kernel methods

Kernel-based methods typically require some properties of the kernel function to be satisfied. The SVM is formulated for PSD kernels. Similarly, interpolation kernel machines require PD kernels to guarantee the invertibility of kernel matrix K . If such requirements are satisfied, these kernel methods can be safely used.

The situation is more complex if these formal requirements are violated. In case of non-PSD kernels the SVM formulation is no longer guaranteed to be convex, thus resulting in a non-convex optimization problem. For interpolation kernel machines only PD kernels can guarantee the invertibility of the kernel matrix K . It is however important to point out that a violation of the formal requirement merely means no guarantee of the applicability of SVM or interpolation kernel machine in general, i.e. for all possible training datasets. Particular training datasets, however, may exist that lead to PSD and PD kernel matrix so such the kernel methods can still be applied in such specific cases.

Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ denote the power set of \mathcal{G} , i.e. all subsets of \mathcal{G} , each representing a dataset of graphs. When working with some kernel method, we consider a set of datasets $\mathcal{P}^*(\mathcal{G}) \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ that contains all datasets in $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ violating the formal requirement of the particular kernel method. These are those datasets that cannot be handled by the standard version of the kernel method (SVM or interpolation kernel machine). \mathcal{P}^* cannot be neglected. Thus, there is a need of developing indefinite kernel methods to cope with such datasets.

Many real-world applications favor the direct use of similarity measures as kernel, most of which are neither PD or PSD. There are several reasons of still using such kernels [28]. For instance, they produce good performance, but it is difficult to prove the formal requirement. In structural pattern recognition, many of the graph kernels [13,16,27] are PSD at best. The need of indefinite kernel methods is thus a real issue.

4.2 Indefinite interpolation kernel machines

There was, to our knowledge, no previous work on infinite interpolation kernel machines yet. Recently, we developed five such methods [39]. A comparative study showed superior performance of two methods called **LSQ** and **CE** over the others. They will be briefly described in the following and used in our experiments.

LSQ method. We aim at finding a subset of training data $X^* \subset X$ of maximum size such that the kernel matrix K^* corresponding to X^* is invertible. This can be easily achieved by determining the rank m of the original kernel matrix K and reducing K to m independent rows, say by Gaussian elimination. These rows after the elimination process directly specify the related m training samples from X that build the reduced training set X^* . Note that we assume a reasonably high rank m in order not to lose too many training samples. Our experimental results show that this requirement is well satisfied.

A straightforward solution here is to use the reduced X^* for training only, i.e. applying Eq. (6) and (7) using K^* . An interesting alternative turns out to

be still using the complete training set X for training in order to keep as much information as possible. After training, only X^* is kept to build the learned interpolation kernel machine. In this case we need to learn the parameters $A_l = (\alpha_{l1}^*, \dots, \alpha_{lm}^*)$, $l = 1, \dots, c$, based on the target values $Y_l = (y_{l1}, \dots, y_{ln})$. The learning task formulated in Eq. (6) now evolves to:

$$K_{nm}A = Y \quad (8)$$

where $K_{nm}(i, j) = k(x_i, x_j)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$, $j = 1, \dots, m$. Because of $n > m$ this is an overdetermined system of linear equations. Thus, it is no longer possible to obtain zero training error. The typical solution is the least-square method that means in our case minimizing:

$$E_{lq} = \|K_{nm}A - Y\|^2 \quad (9)$$

We minimize E_q by using the BFGS optimization algorithm.

CE method. For classification, however, the least-square formulation may not be suitable. Instead, it is general practice to use the cross entropy as loss function. Let $[]_l$ be the l -th row of a matrix. Then, $[K_{nm}A]_l$, see Eq. (8), corresponds to the output vector of the interpolation kernel machine for training sample x_l and $[Y]_l$ the related target vector. The cross entropy loss is defined by:

$$E_{ce} = - \sum_{l=1}^c [Y]_l \cdot \log\{\Gamma([K_{nm}A]_l)\}_l \quad (10)$$

where Γ is the softmax operator that converts a vector to a probability vector and the notation $\{\}_l$ means the l -th element of a vector. This formulation, however, is no longer analytically solvable. We minimize E_{ce} by BFGS optimization algorithm using the least-square solution above as initialization.

4.3 Indefinite support vector machines

Indefinite SVM has been intensively studied before. This is essentially a non-convex optimization problem. The proposed techniques can be divided into four categories: kernel approximation, kernel transformation, non-convex optimization, and Kreĭn space solutions. Methods of the first two categories obtain a PD kernel from an indefinite one so that a convex solver can be applied afterwards.

Kernel approximation: One can derive a PD kernel that is an approximation of a given indefinite kernel (e.g. [33]). The conformal transformation and conformal linear combination proposed in [23] look for a PSD matrix that is the closest to an indefinite matrix (by means of some auxiliary PSD matrix).

Kernel transformation: The indefinite kernel matrix is modified to become PSD. Let K be a real symmetric $n \times n$ indefinite matrix. Its spectral decomposition leads to $K = U_n \Lambda_n U_n^T = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i u_i u_i^T$, where Λ_n is a diagonal matrix of the eigenvalues λ_i of K and U_n is an orthogonal matrix whose columns u_i correspond to the normalized eigenvectors of K . Simple kernel transformation

methods [23,18] include clip (setting negative eigenvalues to zero), shift (eliminating negative eigenvalues by adding a positive constant), flip (flipping the sign of negative eigenvalues), and square (eigenvalues are squared, which is equivalent to using KK^T instead of K).

Non-convex optimization: These optimization techniques can be used to directly deal with indefinite matrices without kernel matrix modification (see [18,36] for detailed discussion). A SMO-type optimization is applied in [5] which is the basis of the popular LIBSVM solver. The recent work [36,38] directly focuses on the non-convex primal form of IKSVM (instead of the dual form) and solves a related problem of difference of convex programming.

Kreĭn space solutions: There exist rather few methods of this category. The works [18] considers IKSVM in Kreĭn spaces, where the positiveness axiom is no longer required in contrast to Hilbert spaces.

Some other methods do not fit the above categorization well. For instance, the authors of [19] view the indefinite kernel as a noisy instance of a true kernel and then learn an explicit solution for the optimal kernel with a tractable convex optimization problem.

Despite this development of indefinite SVM it has been hardly used for graph classification yet. The work [14] is a typical example, which follows the research line of [2]. Many natural similarity functions are not PSD kernels. Instead of squeezing these functions into PSD versions, a theory of learning with well defined “good” similarity functions is proposed. Here it is the place where indefinite SVM should come into play to work with such non-PSD similarity functions. However, only the standard SVM was used in [14]. This is simply a practical way of doing things, as remarked in [16]: “kernel methods, such as SVMs, have been found to work well empirically also with indefinite kernels (Johansson and Dubhashi 2015), without enjoying the guarantees that apply to positive definite kernels”. Doing it this way, however, the geometric interpretation of SVM (i.e. optimal hyperplane classifier by margin maximization) gets lost. Only for the subclass of non conditionally positive definite kernels there exists an alternate geometric interpretation [6] (minimization of distances between convex hulls in pseudo-Euclidean spaces).

5 Experimental results

We have considered 18 graph datasets from various domains (see Table 1 for an overview). Six PSD graph kernels were selected for the experiments: shortest-path kernel [4], neighborhood hash kernel [8], Weisfeiler-Lehman graph kernel [31], tree-based graph decomposition kernel [21], propagation kernel [24], and pyramid match kernel [26]. The main selection criterion are the diverse design paradigms of these kernels. We used the implementations from the graph kernel library GraKeL written in Python [32]. For each pair of dataset and graph kernel, we conducted a ten-fold cross validation and report the average performance.

domain	dataset	# graphs	# classes	avg. # nodes	avg. # edges
Chemistry	BZR	405	2	35.8	38.4
	BZR_MD	306	2	21.3	225.1
	COX2	467	2	41.2	43.5
	COX2_MD	303	2	26.3	335.1
	DHFR	467	2	42.4	44.5
	DHFR_MD	393	2	23.9	283.0
	ER_MD	446	2	21.3	234.9
	MUTAG	188	2	17.9	19.8
Biology	AIDS	2000	2	15.69	16.20
	PROTEINS	1113	2	39.1	72.8
	PROTEINS_full	1113	2	39.1	72.8
	PTC_FM	349	2	14.1	14.5
	PTC_FR	351	2	14.6	15.0
	PTC_MM	336	2	14.0	14.3
	PTC_MR	344	2	14.3	14.7
	Computer Vision	Cuneiform	267	30	21.3
MSRC_9		221	8	40.6	97.9
MSRC_21		563	20	77.5	198.3

Table 1: Description of graph datasets.

IKM. For IKM the PSD graph kernels mostly result in non-invertible kernel matrix so that we need to resort to indefinite IKM methods. Table 2 presents the average classification accuracy of the two indefinite IKM methods. Note that these results are partly taken from [39], which is the methodological backbone for our current work with five indefinite IKM methods and contains experiments on graph datasets and additional UCI non-graph datasets. Here we further increase the number of graph datasets and graph kernels. It can be observed that **CE** tends to perform better than **LSQ**. This is not a surprise since the cross entropy loss is generally a better choice for classification than the least-square error. These results show that the indefinite IKM methods can successfully handle the indefinite cases.

The good performance of IKMs is comprehensible and even expectable. The representer theorem allows us to express the optimal solution of widely used risk minimization problems in the form (2) as linear combination of expansions in terms of the training samples. An interpolation kernel machine basically takes this form of optimal solution, Eq. (3), and directly optimizes its parameters α_i by a suitable loss function and training. In some sense the IKM thus may be understood as an ultimate way of learning based on the representer theorem.

IKM vs. SVM. For a comparative study with SVM one could use its standard version since all used graph kernels are PSD. In our study we do apply indefinite SVMs. In these test cases a convex optimization problem has to be solved.

method dataset	Shortest Path [4]				Neighborhood Hash [8]				Weisfeiler-Lehman [31]			
	LSQ	CE	SVM-SMO	SVM-DC	LSQ	CE	SVM-SMO	SVM-DC	LSQ	CE	SVM-SMO	SVM-DC
BZR	79.9	85.4	80.1	83.4	75.4	76.9	77.9	78.1	78.9	80.4	78.6	78.1
BZR_MD	66.0	66.7	40.9	63.4	62.6	62.1	59.5	63.0	50.3	55.1	43.5	48.3
COX2	78.4	76.9	78.2	78.2	80.1	81.0	78.0	79.5	76.3	79.4	78.2	78.4
COX2_MD	59.8	61.1	46.2	59.5	50.3	52.6	47.9	52.2	47.7	50.6	36.3	43.0
DHFR	72.0	67.6	60.4	66.2	72.4	74.1	74.4	74.8	73.6	75.5	75.2	76.3
DHFR_MD	66.2	65.9	67.9	67.4	58.8	57.8	63.6	60.1	64.1	63.1	63.6	63.6
ER_MD	59.5	60.5	59.2	55.7	65.0	66.1	63.8	65.9	66.3	66.5	64.9	64.9
MUTAG	78.7	80.3	80.3	81.9	87.8	85.1	85.6	86.1	83.5	79.8	78.3	81.4
AIDS	98.3	98.3	99.2	99.3	99.2	99.1	99.3	99.3	95.8	94.0	97.8	98.1
PROTEINS	70.5	70.6	72.0	72.8	65.9	68.8	69.7	68.4	63.9	62.2	69.6	69.8
PROTEINS_full	70.5	70.6	71.9	72.8	66.5	69.1	69.8	68.3	63.7	62.2	69.6	69.8
PTC_FM	59.9	57.0	63.6	59.0	59.6	60.7	61.6	59.6	63.6	63.0	64.2	61.3
PTC_FR	65.5	65.3	67.9	64.4	65.0	65.6	67.3	65.5	65.5	67.0	67.9	67.5
PTC_MM	64.6	61.6	64.0	63.4	63.7	64.6	64.9	64.9	67.0	67.9	66.4	69.1
PTC_MR	53.5	57.3	55.6	60.2	64.5	64.3	62.3	64.8	61.3	60.8	62.3	62.2
Cuneiform	53.9	79.7	64.4	80.8	80.5	80.8	80.5	80.5	80.5	80.5	80.5	80.5
MSRC_9	90.5	90.0	87.8	90.0	92.8	92.8	93.7	92.8	90.5	90.5	85.1	90.1
MSRC_21	75.3	75.2	70.9	76.2	81.7	80.3	80.5	81.0	70.7	70.7	64.0	70.4
average	70.2	71.7	68.4	71.9	71.8	72.3	72.2	72.5	70.2	70.5	69.2	70.7

method dataset	Graph Decomposition [21]				Propagation [24]				Pyramid Match [26]			
	LSQ	CE	SVM-SMO	SVM-DC	LSQ	CE	SVM-SMO	SVM-DC	LSQ	CE	SVM-SMO	SVM-DC
BZR	74.5	74.5	78.6	78.6	75.9	75.7	78.6	79.1	75.7	80.9	81.6	82.9
BZR_MD	62.8	60.5	32.1	32.4	49.7	49.7	48.7	49.7	60.8	60.8	60.7	63.1
COX2	79.2	79.2	78.2	78.2	76.0	79.0	78.2	78.2	77.8	78.2	78.2	76.9
COX2_MD	60.2	60.8	34.4	35.7	50.9	50.6	50.6	50.2	57.8	57.8	57.5	59.4
DHFR	70.8	70.8	61.0	61.0	69.0	74.3	73.6	75.7	67.3	70.0	63.4	68.9
DHFR_MD	65.7	66.4	67.9	67.9	58.0	60.8	63.4	60.5	54.0	54.0	67.9	62.9
ER_MD	54.1	58.0	59.2	59.2	63.2	65.4	65.8	64.3	57.6	57.6	69.9	68.3
MUTAG	77.2	77.2	67.6	74.5	78.7	77.6	70.2	76.1	86.1	83.4	84.5	85.6
AIDS	85.5	85.9	82.9	84.1	91.0	89.9	93.7	95.8	99.5	99.6	99.7	99.7
PROTEINS	52.4	51.0	55.1	57.9	63.8	64.4	70.1	70.5	66.0	70.9	69.5	71.0
PROTEINS_full	63.5	63.3	63.4	57.9	63.0	62.9	69.1	70.0	67.3	69.6	70.6	70.4
PTC_FM	63.9	63.3	64.5	63.3	57.0	59.8	62.2	59.3	59.6	57.3	59.9	60.8
PTC_FR	66.7	67.5	68.4	68.1	65.5	65.5	67.0	64.4	59.0	61.0	67.0	61.5
PTC_MM	67.2	66.9	67.0	67.5	65.8	63.7	64.6	67.3	61.7	62.9	64.6	65.8
PTC_MR	55.8	55.8	58.8	56.4	57.3	62.0	57.1	60.2	55.0	53.6	58.5	55.6
Cuneiform	19.9	75.6	45.9	65.4	80.5	80.5	80.5	80.5	81.3	81.3	80.1	82.0
MSRC_9	79.6	79.6	78.7	83.7	93.7	88.7	91.7	91.4	92.8	92.8	89.1	89.1
MSRC_21	76.4	76.4	60.7	74.8	72.3	71.6	70.7	76.4	72.0	72.0	75.7	79.3
average	65.3	68.5	62.5	64.8	68.4	69.0	69.8	70.5	69.5	70.2	72.1	72.4

Table 2: Performance (%) of indefinite interpolation kernel machines **LSQ** and **CE** on graph datasets. Comparison with indefinite SVMs.

method	LSQ	CE
SVM-SMO	46.3	47.2
SVM-DC	38.9	42.6

Table 3: Detailed comparison of IKM methods with SVMs.

The extended non-convex solvers should come to similar result. Concretely, we selected the SMO-type optimization [5], SVM-SMO, from the popular LIBSVM solver and the recent approach based on difference of convex functions programming [36,38], SVM-DC. SVM-DC has a regularization parameter γ . For a fair comparison we have done a grid search to fix its optimal value.

The performance measures with these indefinite SVMs are also presented in Table 2. Generally, SVM-DC tends to perform better than SVM-SMO. The performance of the variant **CE** is comparable with that of SVM-DC. This similarity in performance can be further detailed by looking at the percentage of test cases where one method performs better than the other one. The total number of test cases is 108 (18 datasets, 6 graph kernels). Table 3 reveals that in 42.6% (47.2%) of test cases, **CE** is in favor compared to SVM-DC (SVM-SMO). Also the slightly weaker variant **LSQ** can outperform SVM-DC (SVM-SMO) in 38.9% (46.3%) of the test cases.

6 Extended experimental protocol

The results above justify a systematic consideration of IKM parallel to the popular SVM for experimentation in graph classification. We thus propose an extended experimental protocol to obtain the maximal possible graph classification performance in a particular application using some graph kernel $k(x, y)$. It consists of different courses of action dependent of the type of graph kernel:

- If $k(x, y)$ is PD, then apply the standard SVM and the standard IKM.
- If $k(x, y)$ is PSD, then apply the standard SVM and some indefinite IKM.
- Otherwise, apply some indefinite SVM and some indefinite IKM.

In each case the applied methods can be compared to select the best one. The first case will rarely happen due to lacking strict PD kernels. In other cases it is also possible to further include additional options, e.g. indefinite SVM in the second case of PSD kernels as done in our work.

7 Conclusion

In this paper have introduced two important aspects, interpolation kernel machine and indefinite kernel methods, which have not received attention in the graph processing community so far. From the results and discussions above we can make the following conclusions:

- The IKM is a good alternative of the popular SVM that is currently omnipresent in kernel-based graph classification.
- Infinite SVMs should be taken into account for non-PSD kernels, see the discussion in Section 4.3.

The first statement was experimentally demonstrated in this work. The second statement is a fundamental one. In practice one should always consider the indefinite SVMs in general because of their formal correctness. Consequently, we have proposed an extended experimental protocol. With this work we contribute to increasing the methodological plurality in the graph processing community.

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